

1 Review

2 Biopsychosocial Rehabilitation in Chronic Mental Illnesses: 3 The Awareness Stage

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Abstract

Psychosocial rehabilitation plays a central role in the recovery of individuals with severe mental illness, targeting functionality across psychological, social, and occupational domains. Despite the existence of multiple rehabilitation models worldwide, Romania lacks a standardized, evidence-based framework. This study reviews contemporary literature to identify key components of effective biopsychosocial rehabilitation. A total of 3235 articles were screened, with 40 included for analysis. Findings highlight the effectiveness of integrated interventions such as cognitive remediation, family psychoeducation, and community-based treatment. Biopsychosocial factors—including symptom severity, social support, and community integration—are directly associated with life satisfaction. The results support the development of a structured, adaptable rehabilitation model that could improve outcomes and reduce disparities in mental healthcare systems.

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1. Introduction

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Although rehabilitation models exist globally, Romania lacks standardized and procedural frameworks. Current practices involve isolated interventions insufficient for meaningful comparison with international systems. Poor adherence and fragmented care further complicate outcomes [1,2].

This study aims to synthesize recent literature to identify effective strategies in biopsychosocial rehabilitation. We hypothesize that structured rehabilitation models improve outcomes, reduce relapse rates, and achieve results comparable to international standards. Additionally, identifying the most effective interventions may support the development of evidence-based national policies.

2. Materials and Methods

A literature review was conducted using PubMed, Google Scholar, PsycINFO, Web of Science, and related databases, covering publications from 2017 to present. A total of 3235 articles were screened; after removing duplicates and excluding non-relevant topics, 40 articles were included.

Studies focusing on aging-related cognitive decline or dementia stigma were excluded [16]. The analysis was structured into two sections: lower-relevance studies and high-impact studies related to psychosocial rehabilitation in severe mental disorders.

3. Results

3.1 Physical Activity and Adjunctive Therapies

Physical exercise has demonstrated benefits in both prevention and treatment of mental disorders, including augmentation of antidepressant effects [12,13]. These interventions significantly contribute to improved quality of life.

Group-based physical activity also enhances social integration and reduces morbidity and mortality in individuals with severe mental illness [22].

3.2 Rehabilitation Models and Global Variability

Rehabilitation approaches vary depending on national policies, resources, and workforce expertise.

FIGURE 1: Factors involved in the implementation of biopsychosocial rehabilitation models

However, no universally accepted evidence-based model exists [10].

Effective interventions identified include:

- Assertive Community Treatment
- Cognitive remediation
- Family psychoeducation
- Social skills training[6,7]

WPA outlines the guidelines for psychosocial rehabilitation in 2016: training emotional skills, training cognitive skills, training social skills, functioning in the community

FIGURE 2: Goals of psychosocial rehabilitation established by the WPA

3.3 Biopsychosocial Factors and Quality of Life

Life satisfaction is strongly associated with psychiatric symptoms, social support, and community integration [17]. Social functioning plays a critical role in recovery, often exceeding the impact of symptom severity [18].

Insight into illness is another key factor influencing outcomes, adherence, and engagement in rehabilitation [14].

Figure 3 CATIE Trial – Insight and quality of life discrepancy analysis.

3.4 Community-Based and Meta-Community Care

80 The “meta-community” model extends care beyond hospitalization, integrating ser-
81 vices into everyday environments [9]. In England, such programs reduced symptom se-
82 verity by up to 65% and facilitated return to employment.

83 Integrated healthcare models combining psychiatric and somatic care improve both
84 morbidity and mortality [26]. Home-based care models further enhance adherence and
85 reduce relapse [36].

86 December 2025 brings to the online scientific environment, in the Journal of Clinical
87 Psychiatry, an article summarizing the conclusions of a working group on Psychosocial
88 intervention and regaining functionality in schizophrenia – current opportunities and
89 guidelines for recommendations in future clinical guidelines, guidelines that include 4
90 main trajectories for functionality in schizophrenia. In addition to the aspect of the person
91 “per se” consisting of the internal environment and behavior, it is also recommended to
92 address the comorbidities but also the social, family context through psychosocial inter-
93 ventions scientifically documented as effective. [41].
94

95 3.5 Emerging Perspectives

96 Digital behavior and virtual social life are increasingly relevant but insufficiently
97 studied factors influencing functioning [24]. Additionally, family involvement and psy-
98 choeducation significantly improve care outcomes [21].

99 Table 1Key psychosocial and clinical factors in the management of severe mental ill-
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103 4. Discussion

104 The findings highlight that effective rehabilitation requires a dual focus: individual-
105 level recovery and community integration [3,4]. Current evidence emphasizes the superi-
106 ority of multidisciplinary, biopsychosocial approaches over purely pharmacological strat-
107 egies.

108 A central issue remains the lack of standardized implementation. While numerous
109 interventions demonstrate efficacy, their fragmented application limits impact. Cultural
110 and systemic differences also influence outcomes, suggesting the need for adaptable
111 frameworks [11].

112 The concept of “well-being” rather than more symptom reduction is increasingly rec-
113 ognized as a central objective in psychiatric care [15].

114 5. Conclusions

- 115 1. Psychosocial rehabilitation is effective, significantly improving quality of life
116 and reducing morbidity [6,7].
- 117 2. Romania lacks a standardized model, highlighting the need for evidence-based
118 frameworks.
- 119 3. Global variability suggests that flexible, adaptable models are most appropri-
120 ate.
- 121 4. Integrated approaches targeting both individual and community are essential
122 [10].
- 123 5. Evidence-based interventions, including psychoeducation and cognitive ther-
124 apies, enhance functional outcomes.
- 125 6. Biopsychosocial factors such as social support and integration are key determi-
126 nants of recovery [17].

The development of a structured rehabilitation model could significantly improve outcomes and reduce inequalities in mental health care.

.FIGURES & TABLES

Figure 1 Factors involved in the implementation of biopsychosocial rehabilitation models.

Figure 2 Goals of psychosocial rehabilitation established by the World Psychiatric Association (WPA).

Figure 3 CATIE Trial – Insight and quality of life discrepancy analysis.

Table 1 Key psychosocial and clinical factors in the management of severe mental illness.

6. Patents

There will be patents resulting from the work in this reported manuscript. A National Guide for Biopsychosocial Rehabilitation in severe mental health disease, based on a good clinical practice model. And further to constitute the legal basis for the protocols imposed by the Health Insurance House (CNAS) in the recommendations for addressing chronic mental illness, so that the actions in this model are reimbursed by the CNAS.

Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

WPA	World Psychiatric Association
CNAS	Health Insurance House

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